

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

Martin Burgi, Lisa Hagen and Nicole Lieb

Research Center for Public Procurement Law and Administrative Cooperations
Ludwig Maximilians University of Munich

Partners

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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INFORMATION

Eurac Research
Viale Druso/Drususallee, 1
39100 Bolzano/Bozen – Italy

logov@eurac.edu
www.logov-rise.eu

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATION

Eurac Research: Karl Kössler

WP 1 – Local Responsibilities and Public Services

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi

WP 2 – Local Financial Arrangements

Universidad Autónoma de Madrid: Francisco Velasco Caballero

WP 3 – Structure of Local Government

University of Fribourg: Eva Maria Belser

WP 4 – Intergovernmental Relations of Local Government

NALAS – Network of Associations of Local Authorities of South East Europe: Elton Stafa

WP 5 – People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making

Ximpulse GmbH: Erika Schläppi

EDITORIAL TEAM

LMU Munich: Martin Burgi, Lisa Hagen, Nicole Lieb
Eurac Research: Karl Kössler, Theresia Morandell, Caterina Salvo, Annika Kress, Petra Malferttheiner

GRAPHIC DESIGN

Eurac Research: Alessandra Stefanut

COVER PHOTO

Leonhard Niederwimmer/Pixabay

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People's Participation in Local Decision-Making

6.3. Local and Interest-Driven Parties or Independent Groups of Voters

Lea Bosch, *Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*

Relevance of the Practice

Citizen-oriented local politics is characterized in particular by focusing on the main political issues of a single municipality, which is why independent groups of voters (i.e. Townhall Parties, Independent Voters' Association, Voters' Community, Voters' Association, Voting Block, Political Union, Political Association, Citizens' Association, Citizens' List, Non-party members) frequently appear alongside traditional parties at the local level. These are mergers of individual citizens of the municipality to pursue certain municipal political concerns. In certain – mainly rural – regions (e.g. Baden-Württemberg and Bavaria), they sometimes account for up to 44 per cent of all local councils (*Gemeinderat*) and 24 per cent of all county councils (*Kreisrat*) of elected representatives in local governments and even provide mayors. They are to be distinguished from 'Other Political Associations' (*Sonstige Politische Vereinigung, SPV*), which are – according to paragraph 8(1) EuWG (European Election Law) – enabled to run for the European Parliament and are therefore not a typical appearance in local governments.

Description of the Practice

Voter groups are not parties within the meaning of paragraph 2(1) PartG. Despite the fact that the Federal Republic of Germany is formed as a parties' state, the voter groups are authorized to take part in all elections to local governments, especially because of Article 28(2) of the Basic Law (BL).¹⁷⁷ The principles of universality and equality of election laid down in Article 38(1) BL maintain the right to nominate candidates in general; prima facie it is not limited to parties. Thus, in conjunction with the local self-government guarantee (*Selbstverwaltungsgarantie*) in Article 28(2) BL it is maintained that also 'local voter groups pursuing only local interests [i.e. issues of a single municipality] [have] the right to nominate candidates and their candidates must be guaranteed equal opportunities to participate in local elections'.¹⁷⁸ In particular, they

¹⁷⁷ BVerfGE 11, 266, recital 24. Also, see above in section A. 2. of the General Introduction to the System of Local Government in Germany.

¹⁷⁸ Guidelines BVerfGE 11, 266; furthermore, with regard to groups of voters with regard to the generality and equality of the election BVerfGE 121, 108; 78, 350 (358); 99, 69 (78).

are to be treated equal to the parties with regard to their financing and tax advantages.¹⁷⁹ In general, the prerequisites for a voters' group candidacy are a legal foundation, a proper statute and proof of the democratic appointment of the executive committee. Frequently, voter groups organize themselves in the legal form of a registered association (*eingetragener Verein e.V.*).

Local self-government has a long legal and actual tradition in Germany. Already during the Weimar Republic numerous local voter groups existed, which were then purely factual restricted to local interests.¹⁸⁰ This continues up to this day. It is in the nature of local self-government to depend on the support of fellow citizens and to require adaptation to the specific local needs of the community. Voter groups exist in both rural and urban areas, although their influence and significance in rural local government (RLG) is usually stronger than in urban local government (ULG). That is because well-known citizens, who are particularly familiar with their local circumstances, become more important in local politics as municipalities get smaller. Also, this increased influence in rural areas is particularly evident in the many communities where voters' associations provide the mayor or in some cases even make up a dominant part of the local government. In large cities, on the other hand, groups of voters initially had less weight. However, current developments such as ongoing gentrification, the issue of migration as well as concerns due to climate change seem to indicate a change in ULG as well (see below).

Voters' groups often arise from citizens' initiatives, i.e. associations with specific topics.¹⁸¹ The positions of voter groups vary widely and are both local and issue-specific. However, they do have a high degree of commonality in their advocacy of strengthening plebiscitary elements. In some cases, voter groups are a kind of melting pot of non-party, but politically interested and committed citizens who do not want to join a party but want to combine – usually – forces of moderate conservative (i.e. middle-class) opinions. Since local election law is a *Länder* competence, there are considerable differences in the legal bases for the participation of a voters' group in a local election. The more personal the voting process is designed (i.e., strong elements of the personality vote), the more likely non-party candidates are to have a chance of success.¹⁸² This is the case in almost all *Länder*-local election laws: They allow splitting and cumulating votes, thus highly developed elements of the personality vote are to be found.

¹⁷⁹ Hans H von Arnim, 'Werden kommunale Wählergemeinschaften im politischen Wettbewerb diskriminiert?' (1999) 114 DVBl 417, 421ff; Martin Morlok and Heike Merten, 'Partei genannt Wählergemeinschaft – Probleme im Verhältnis von Parteien und Wählergemeinschaften' (2011) 64 DÖV 125, 128ff.

¹⁸⁰ BVerfGE 11, 266, recital 35.

¹⁸¹ See report section 6.2. on Citizens' Petitions for Referendum Against Essential Large-Scale Infrastructure Projects in Urban Areas.

¹⁸² Martin Burgi, *Kommunalrecht* (6th edn CH Beck 2019) para 11 Rn16.

Assessment of the Practice

Though municipal election turnout is declining,¹⁸³ most recent developments show an increased politicization focused on specific topics, which can often be attributed to emotional and short-term issues. Citizens' petitions for referendum (see above) and citizens' initiatives occur more often, proving the increase of participation in local decision-making in general. This may lead to an increased appearance of local voter groups or at least a higher involvement in such already existing groups. In addition, there is widespread dissatisfaction with the traditional political parties, which thus struggle in fulfilling their constitutional duties (Article 21 BL) such as the recruitment of upcoming mandate holders and focusing on long-term issues. As voters' associations gain relevance, voices become louder that demand the imposition of the duties of parties on the voters' associations as well.¹⁸⁴ Actually, this is a purely local political phenomenon, but in the course of time, parties have already emerged from such voter groups, as only parties can participate in elections to the *Bundestag* or a *Landtag* (most prominent examples: Freie Wähler, Bündnis 90/Die Grünen). Thus, independent groups of voters can become highly relevant also for other sorts of participation.

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¹⁸³ Angelika Vetter, 'Kommunale Wahlbeteiligung im Bundesländervergleich – Politische Institutionen und ihre Folgen' (2008) 61 DÖV 885: the voter turnout in local elections is roughly at 45% (comparison: in federal elections around 80%).

¹⁸⁴ Morlok and Merten, 'Partei genannt Wählergemeinschaft', above, 133f.

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Contacts

Local Government and the Changing
Urban-Rural Interplay
www.logov-rise.eu
logov@eurac.edu

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